

PRE-ELECTION AWARENESS OF YOUTH ABOUT PANCHAYATI RAJ INSTITUTIONS IN HIMACHAL PRADESH: A CASE STUDY

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Paper Received On: 21 October 2025

Peer Reviewed On: 25 November 2025

Published On: 01 December 2025

Abstract

The present study examines the level of pre-election awareness among youth regarding Panchayati Raj Institutions (PRIs) in Himachal Pradesh, with special reference to Kangra District. A descriptive research design was adopted for the study. Primary data were collected using a structured questionnaire from randomly selected youth respondents. The study focuses on youth awareness related to the structure, functions, electoral process, and voting rights of Panchayati Raj Institutions prior to election. It also analyses the influence of media exposure, political interest, and local political discussions on the level of pre-election awareness among youth. The study highlights the need for systematic and focused awareness programmes before Panchayati Raj elections to strengthen and informed youth engagement in grassroots democracy.

Keywords: Pre-Election, Awareness, Youth, Panchayati Raj Institutions, Himachal Pradesh

Introduction

Panchayati Raj Institutions (PRIs) form the foundation of democratic governance in India. The 73rd Constitutional Amendment Act, 1992, gave constitutional recognition to PRIs. It also ensured direct citizen participation in local governance. PRIs promote decentralized governance and local self-government. It enables people to participate in planning, administration, and developmental process. Youth play vital role in strengthening democracy. Their awareness and participation in Panchayati elections ensure transparency and accountability. Therefore, studying youth awareness of PRIs before elections is essential to understand their engagement in grassroots democracy.

LOCALE OF THE STUDY

The present study is confined to the Kangra district of Himachal Pradesh. It is one of the hilly state of India. After a long struggle Himachal Pradesh gained full-fledged statehood on 25th January , 1971 and became the 18th state of Indian Union. Presently, Himachal Pradesh is administratively divided into 12 districts, 91 development blocks and its rural local governance system comprises 3,615 Gram Panchayats. The Kangra district is one of the largest district of the state, plays a significant role in this structure and is administratively organized into 18 development blocks. The district has a total of 814 Gram Panchayats, which play a vital role in rural governance and local development. Among these, Baijnath is an important Development Block of Kangra district and comprises 45 Gram Panchayats, playing a significant role in local administration and rural development.

Panchayati Raj in Himachal Pradesh

The new State of Himachal Pradesh adopted the Punjab village Panchayat Act 1952. The Himachal Pradesh Act, 1952 was replaced in 1968, when the State Legislature passed a new Panchayati Raj Act. This Act three-tier system of Panchayati Raj Gram Sabha at village, Panchayat Samiti at block and Zila Parishad at the district level was adopted. According to H.P. Panchayat Raj Act, 1968 all members of Gram Panchayat shall be elected directly by members of Gram Sabha among themselves. Later on, Himachal Pradesh enacted a new Panchayati Raj legislation, the Himachal Panchayati Raj Act, 1994 in conformity with provisions of the Constitution (73rd Amendment) Act 1992. This Act has provision for three tier system as Gram Panchayat, Panchayat Samiti and Zila Parishad at village, block and district levels respectively. Presently Himachal Pradesh, the Panchayati Raj Institution elections originally scheduled for December 2025 and January 2026 were postponed due to extensive monsoon related damage to rural infrastructure, including widespread road disruptions across the state, prompting the government to invoke provisions of the Disaster Management Act to defer the polls until connectivity is restored. This delay underscores the importance of pre-election awareness, particularly among youth. Owing to this, sustained awareness during such periods is essential to maintain democratic engagement and ensure participation when elections are eventually conducted.

Objectives of the Study

- 1) To assess the level of awareness among youth about Panchayati Raj Institutions.
- 2) To examine youth knowledge regarding PRI elections.
- 3) To identify sources of information influencing youth awareness.

4) To suggest measures for improving pre-election awareness.

Research Methodology

The present study is empirical in nature and is based on primary data. The data were collected from youth respondents in Baijnath Development Block of Kangra district, Himachal Pradesh. The Baijnath Development Block has total 45 Gram Panchayats. A structured questionnaire was used as the main tool for data collection to obtain information relevant to the objectives of the study. A total sample of 117 youth respondents was chosen through the random sampling method. The respondents represented diverse caste, gender, and educational backgrounds, ensuring adequate social representation. The data were analyzed through using simple statistical tools such as percentage and the findings were interpreted accordingly.

SECTION A: Social Background of the Respondents

Prior to data interpretation, it is necessary to examine the social background of the respondents, as it provides the contextual framework of the study. The social background of respondents influences their level of awareness, attitude, and participation in Panchayati Raj Institutions. Analysing these characteristics enables a clearer understanding of the data and ensures a more meaningful interpretation of the research findings.

Table 1.1: Age –wise Distribution of Respondents

Age	No of Respondents	%age
18-20	99	84.6
21-23	18	15.4
24-26	-	-

The data in the table 1.1 indicates that a large majority of the respondents (84.6%) belong to the age group of 18–20 years. It reflects that the study is predominantly represented by younger adults. In contrast, 15.4% of the respondents fall within the 21–23 years age group, indicating comparatively lower participation from this category. No one respondent was recorded in the 24–26 years age group, as reflected by the absence of data in this category. The age-wise distribution therefore reveals a clear concentration of respondents in the lower age bracket.

Table 1.2: Gender –wise Distribution of Respondents

Gender	No of Respondents	%age
Male	29	24.8
Female	88	75.2

It is evident from the table 1.2 that female respondents constitute the majority, accounting for 75.2% of the total sample. In comparison, male respondents represent 24.8% of the total

respondents. This distribution indicates a higher participation of females than males in the study.

Table 1.3: Caste-wise Distribution of Respondents

Caste	No of Respondents	%age
General	42	35.9
SC	47	40.2
ST	20	17.1
Others	8	6.8

The data in the table 1.3 reveals that Scheduled Caste (SC) respondents constitute the largest proportion of the sample (40.2%), followed by the respondents from the General category (35.9%). Scheduled Tribe (ST) respondents account for 17.1%, indicating moderate representation. The category of Others Castes comprises 6.8% of the total respondents, reflecting comparatively lower participation. Overall, the caste-wise distribution indicates that the study is based on a socially heterogeneous sample, ensuring representation from major caste categories.

Table 1.4: Education Qualifications of Respondents

Response	No of Respondents	%age
Plus Two	88	75.2
Graduation	23	19.7
Post Graduate	4	3.4
Professional/Vocational	2	1.7

The data in table 1.4 shows that the majority of respondents (75.2%) have completed their higher secondary level of education. A smaller proportion 19.7%, holds a graduate degree and only 3.4% respondents are postgraduates. A minimal number of respondents (1.7%) have professional or vocational qualifications.

Section B: Awareness about Panchayati Raj Institutions

Awareness of Panchayati Raj Institutions is crucial because these local bodies form the foundation of grassroots democracy in India. Knowledge about PRIs enables citizens, especially youth, to actively participate in local governance, exercise their voting rights effectively and hold elected representatives accountable. It also helps in understanding the roles, responsibilities and functions of Gram Panchayats. It is also promoting transparency and efficiency in decision-making.

Table 2.1: Awareness of Respondents Regarding Election of Gram Panchayat Members?

Response	No of Respondents	%age.
Gram Sabha	109	93.1
Govt Officials	3	2.5
Political Parties	1	1
Don't Know	4	3.4

Table 2.1 presents the respondents' awareness regarding the election of Gram Panchayat members. The data indicate that a vast majority of respondents (93.1%) correctly identified that villagers (Gram Sabha) elect the Panchayat members, reflecting a high level of awareness about local democratic processes. A very small number of respondents viewed that government officials (3%) or political parties (1%) are responsible for the elections. In addition to this, 3.4% of respondents reported that they did not know who elects the Gram Panchayat members.

Table 2.2: Awareness of Respondents about lowest tier of Panchayati Raj

	No of Respondents	%age
Gram Panchayat	99	84.6
Panchayat Samiti	6	5.1
Zila Parishad	2	1.7
Dont Know	10	8.6

The table 2.2 shows respondents' awareness of the lowest tier of the Panchayati Raj system. A majority (84.6%) correctly identified the Gram Panchayat as the lowest tier, while a few respondents mentioned Panchayat Samiti (5.1%) or Zila Parishad (1.7%) as lowest tier of the PRIs. However, 8.6% of respondents did not know about three tier system of PRIs. This indicates that most respondents have a clear understanding of the basic structure of Panchayati Raj institutions.

Table 2.3: Awareness of Respondents about Functions of Gram Sabha

Response	No of Respondents	%age
Yes	75	64.1
No	28	23.9
To some extent	14	12

Table 2.3 shows that 64.1% of respondents are aware of the functions of the Gram Sabha, 23.9% are unaware, and 12% respondents had partial knowledge about Gram Sabha which indicates a moderate level of understanding. These findings highlight the need for targeted awareness programs to enhance civic participation and active decision-making in local governance.

Table 2.4: Awareness of Respondents about the reservation provisions (for women, SC/ST) in Panchayati Raj Institutions

Response	No of Respondents	%age
Yes	95	81.19
No	8	6.84
Partially	14	11.97

Table 2.4 presents the respondents awareness of reservation provisions for women and SC/ST in Panchayati Raj Institutions. The data reveals that a majority of respondents (81.19%) are aware of these provisions, indicating a strong understanding of affirmative measures in local governance. A small proportion of respondents (6.84%) reported no awareness, whereas 11.97% were only partially aware about the reservation provisions for women and SC/ST in Panchayati Raj Institutions.

Section C: Pre- Election Awareness and Information Sources

Pre-election awareness is the knowledge of the citizens about an upcoming election. It includes information about candidates, political parties and voting procedures. It helps people to cast their vote responsibly and make their desired choices. It also strengthens accountability in governance and community welfare. It has great importance for youth and first-time voters, to encourage their participation and builds confidence in democracy.

Table 3.1: Sources of Information about PRIs Elections

Response	No of Respondents	%age
Social Media	44	37.6
Television	13	11.1
Family/School/College	54	46.2
Gram Sabha/Local Meeting	6	5.1

The table 3.1 shows the sources of information respondents rely on for Panchayati Raj Institution (PRI) elections. A majority (46.2%) obtain information from family, school, or college, followed by social media (37.6%) and Gram Sabha or local meetings (30.8%). Television serves as a source of information for 5.1% of respondents. These findings indicate that informal and community-based sources play a significant role in spreading awareness about PRI elections.

Table 3.2: Attended Pre elections Awareness Programme

Response	No of Respondents	%age
Yes	42	35.9
No	75	64.1

The table 3.2 shows that 35.9% of respondents have attended pre-election awareness programs, whereas 64.1% have not attended these awareness programme. This indicates that

a majority of respondents were not exposed to organized electoral awareness initiatives, reflecting limited direct engagement with pre-election activities.

Table 3.3: Willingness to Vote in the Upcoming PRIs Elections

Response	No of Respondents	%age
Yes	76	65
No	17	14.5
Undecided	24	20.5

The table 3.3 shows respondents' willingness to vote in the upcoming Panchayati Raj Institution elections. A majority of 65% expressed their intention to cast their vote, whereas 14.5% not interested and 20.5% were undecided. This reflects that while most respondents are willing to participate in the elections, a significant portion remains uncertain or reluctant.

Table 3.4: Panchayati Raj Elections are important for local development

Response	No of Respondents	%age
Very Important	83	70.9
Somewhat Important	31	26.5
Not Important	3	2.6

The table 3.4 indicates respondents' views on the importance of Panchayati Raj elections for local development. A majority of respondents 70.9% considered them very important, 26.5% view them as somewhat important, and only 2.6% feel that elections are not important. It reflects that youth considered Panchayati Raj elections are very important for local development, highlighting widespread recognition of their role in effective governance and community welfare.

Sections E: Barriers and Suggestions

Table 4.1: Main Reasons for low Youth participation in PRIs Elections

Response	No of Respondents	%age
Lack of Awareness	51	43.6
Lack of Interest	22	18.8
Busy Schedule	15	12.8
Lack of Trust in Local Leadership	29	24.8

The table highlights the main reasons for low youth participation in Panchayati Raj elections. The majority of respondents (43.6%) cited lack of awareness, 24.8% reported lack of trust in local leadership, 18.8% mentioned lack of interest, and 12.8% pointed to a busy schedule. It reflects that insufficient awareness and trust issues are the primary barriers preventing active youth engagement in local governance.

Table 4.2: Measures can improve Youth Awareness about PRIs

Response	No of Respondents	%age
Awareness campaign	13	11.1
Social Media Outreach	11	9.4
School/College Based Programmes	15	12.8
Gram Sabha involvement	9	7.7
All of the Above	65	59

The table presents respondents' views on measures to improve youth awareness about Panchayati Raj Institutions. A majority of 59% suggested all of the above i.e Awareness campaign, Social media Outreach, School/College based programmes and Gram Sabha involvement measures combined, while smaller proportions recommended school/college-based programmes (12.8%), awareness campaigns (11.1%), social media outreach (9.4%), or Gram Sabha involvement (7.7%) individually. It reflects that respondents prefer a comprehensive approach to enhance youth participation and knowledge about PRIs.

Table 4.3: Interest in Contesting PRIs Elections in Future

Response	No of Respondents	%age
Yes	62	53
No	15	12.8
Undecided	40	34.2

The table 4.3 shows respondents' interest in contesting Panchayati Raj elections in the future. A majority of 53% expressed willingness to contest, 12.8% did not wish to participate, and 34.2% were undecided. It reflects that while more than half of the respondents are inclined toward active political participation. A substantial portion remains uncertain about entering local governance.

Findings

The study highlights that youth in Block, Kangra District in Himachal Pradesh have a fairly good understanding of Panchayati Raj Institutions. Most respondents correctly identified villagers (Gram Sabha) as the electors and recognized the Gram Panchayat as the foundational tier of local governance. While awareness of Gram Sabha functions and reservation provisions for women and SC/ST is commendable. Respondents primarily access information through family, schools, colleges, social media, and local meetings. Never the less many have not participated in formal pre-election awareness programs. Most youth expressed a willingness to vote and acknowledged the importance of PRI elections for local

development. The root challenges are the lack of active participation which include limited awareness, lack of interest, busy schedules, and distrust in local leadership.

Suggestions

- ❖ Conduct awareness campaigns and educational programs in schools, colleges, and communities to highlight the importance of Panchayati Raj Institutions (PRIs).
- ❖ Utilize social media, digital platforms, and online engagement to disseminate information effectively among youth.
- ❖ Encourage youth leadership, mentorship programs, and representation in local governance bodies.
- ❖ Promote Gram Sabha participation, workshops, and community events to engage young citizens directly.
- ❖ Implement incentive-based initiatives and interactive programs to motivate youth participation.
- ❖ Include civic education on local governance in school and college curricula to build long-term awareness.

Conclusions:

Pre-election awareness plays a pivotal role in enabling youth to participate effectively in Panchayati Raj elections. Although, youth have an adequate understanding of electoral processes, Gram Panchayat functions, reservation provisions, gaps in knowledge, interest, and engagement remain significant. Addressing these gaps requires the implementation of targeted educational programs, structured civic engagement initiatives, awareness campaigns and mentorship opportunities. Strengthening pre-election awareness can empower youth to make informed decisions, actively participate in local governance, and assume leadership roles. Ultimately, fostering meaningful youth involvement is essential for enhancing democratic governance, ensuring accountability, and promoting sustainable development at the grassroots level.

REFERENCES

- Singh, Mian Goverdhan. (1994). History, Culture, Economy of Himachal Pradesh, Minerva Book House, Shimla.*
- Singh, S., Misra, Suresh. (1993), Legislative frame work of Panchayat Raj in India, Intellectual Publishing House New Delhi.*
- Department of Rural Development and Panchayat Raj Himachal Pradesh. (1970). Panchayati Raj Act, 1968: Act, 19 of 1970, Shimla.*
- Department of Rural Development and Panchayat Raj. (1988). Himachal Pradesh Panchayati Raj (Amendment) Act, 1988, Shimla.*

Department of Rural Development and Panchayat Raj. (1991). Himachal Pradesh Panchayati Raj (Amendment) Act, (1991), Shimla.

Department of Rural Development and Panchayat Raj. (1994). Himachal Pradesh Panchayati Raj Act. (1994), Act. No. 12 of 1994, Shimla.

Aslam, M. Panchayati Raj in India. New Delhi: National Book Trust, 2007